

SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES COMPASS

NAVIGATING DIGITAL RESEARCH SERVICES

A COLLECTION OF THE DATA,
SOFTWARE AND COMPUTING
SERVICES AVAILABLE AT THE
DUTCH NATIONAL
INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS
FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND
HUMANITIES RESEARCHERS

April 2024

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PLANNING YOUR PROJECT

In the planning phase, you should think about the kinds of data you will be handling and the kind of software you will develop, use, or reuse. This phase also includes thinking about how to process data and software, which analysis tools and environments to use, and how to make research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

Check out [The Turing Way](#) for an extensive guide on reproducible research, including data and software management.

Check out the [CESSDA DMEG](#) for a guide on Research Data Management (RDM) specifically targeted at Social Science researchers.

Consider consulting research data and software experts at the Digital Competence Centers.

DATA

- Find suitable Data Management Plans (DMP). Check your local institute's policy or consult a DMP Tool (e.g. [DMPOnline](#)).
- Check how you will make your data FAIR at the start of your project using the [FAIRAwareTool](#).

SOFTWARE

- Read the [Practical guide to Software Management Plans](#) to help you manage your software outputs.
- Check recommendations on how you can make your software FAIR using [FAIRsoftware.eu](#).

COMPUTE

- In case your own computer does not have sufficient computing power, [check](#) how SURF can provide you with additional cloud or high performance computing capacity, including [consultancy](#).

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COLLECT, ORGANISE & DOCUMENT

You need to think about how to properly collect, organise and document your data, metadata and software in order to facilitate transparency and reuse.

DATA

- Consider the use of open file formats for data that you use and produce, try to follow guidelines on [preferred formats](#).
- To make it easier to archive and share your data later on, please consult DANS' guidelines on [documenting data](#) before depositing your data.

SOFTWARE

- Search the [Research Software Directory](#) for existing software that can be used to collect data.
- Consider using open software tools ([Python](#), [R](#), [JASP](#)) rather than proprietary equivalents (MATLAB, SPSS).
- If you need commercial software, check your institution's software catalogue or [SURFspot](#) for discounted rates.
- [Apply to collaborate](#) with the eScience Center on your project's research software.

COMPUTE

- In case your own computer does not have sufficient computing power, [check](#) how SURF can provide you with additional cloud or high performance computing capacity, including [consultancy](#).

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PROCESS YOUR DATA & COLLABORATE WITH OTHERS

Data processing and analysis is an important step in the research process. Often, you don't work on your data in isolation, but collaborate with colleagues on a common dataset, analysis pipeline or software project.

DATA

- Check your institution's policy and repository for storing data during data collection and processing.
- You can store, synchronise and share your data securely with [SURFdrive](#), your personal cloud storage.
- If you need large quantities of storage, e.g. for audio or video, you can use the online [Object store](#).
- Consider using [Research Drive](#) if you work collaboratively as a team, e.g. with external parties. Check whether [your institution has Research Drive](#).
- Use [Filesender](#) if you want to send and receive files up to 1TB quickly, securely and easily.
- Check if there is a training on data analysis through [one of the institutes in the Netherlands](#).
- Consider storing your data in open file formats, try to follow guidelines on [preferred formats](#).

SOFTWARE

- Consider sharing your code as early as possible using a [publicly accessible repository with version control](#).
- Check if there is a training on research software development through [one of the institutes in the Netherlands](#).
- Read about good software development practices and collaborative software development in [The Turing Way](#).
- [Apply to collaborate](#) with the eScience Center on your project's research software.

COMPUTE

In case your own computer does not have sufficient computing power, [check](#) how SURF can provide you with additional cloud or high performance computing capacity, including [consultancy](#).

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STORE (DURING RESEARCH)

This section is about storing your research project while you are still working on it. Often you will use the resources and policies provided at your institution.

DATA

- Check your institution's policy and repository for storing data during research (e.g. [DataverseNL](#) if applicable).
- You can store, synchronise and share your data securely with [SURFdrive](#), your personal cloud storage.
- If you need large quantities of storage, e.g. for audio or video, you can use the online [Object store](#).
- Consider using [Research Drive](#) if you work collaboratively as a team, e.g. with external parties.
- Check whether [your institution has Research Drive](#).

SOFTWARE

- Check your institution's policy and repository for storing software during research.
- If you are using [GitHub](#) or [GitLab](#), display your software project in its research context using the [Research Software Directory \(RSD\)](#).
- [Check](#) whether your institution is connected to the RSD.

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ARCHIVE AND PUBLISH

After you are done with data collection, analysis, or software development, you will want to archive your project and (potentially) share it with your colleagues or other researchers in your field for reuse. Choosing sustainable trustworthy repositories to archive and publish your data and software is crucial to ensure they are available for the long term.

DATA

- Archive and publish your data in your institutional repositories if available (e.g. [DataverseNL](#)).
- If your institute does not facilitate data archiving or if you want to make use of expertise and data curation, use the [DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities](#).
- Consult the [DANS guidelines for archiving and publishing data](#).
- Ensure that the repository of your choice assigns a [Persistent Identifier](#) to your data.
- Archive your data in open file formats following guidelines on [preferred formats](#).
- If you have large amounts of data, check with your institution if you can use the [SURF Data Archive](#) for inexpensive, secure, long-term storage.

SOFTWARE

- If you are using [GitHub](#) or [GitLab](#), display your software project in its research context using the [Research Software Directory](#) (RSD).
- Archive the software in Zenodo, publish it, or add it to a [community registry](#).
- Ensure that you include a CITATION.cff file in your software repository to make your software citable. You can use the tool [CFFinit](#) to generate such a file.

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DISCOVER

You can find existing data and software through various portals which will help you select available resources to (re)use in your project.

DATA

- For Social Sciences data you can search the [ODISSEI Portal](#) which includes datasets from Dutch data providers, e.g. from the [DANS Data Stations](#), [DataverseNL](#), [LISS_panel](#) and [CBS microdata](#).
- On a European level you can use the [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#) to find datasets from European Social Science Data Archives.
- For Humanities data you can search in [CLARIAH's ineo](#) portal.

SOFTWARE

- Find software in the [Research Software Directory](#).

ONLINE VERSION

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ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT

This document gives an overview of the research data, software and computing services provided by [SURF](#), [DANS](#) and the [Netherlands eScience Center](#). It will help you navigate these services.

Although a number of the resources mentioned in this document are domain-agnostic, this document focuses on resources relevant to the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research community in the Netherlands.

ATTRIBUTION

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